

D1.9 Data Management Plan

115966 – PREFER

**Patient Preferences in
Benefit-Risk Assessments
during the Drug Life Cycle**

[WP1 – Project Management]

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Version	Date	Description
V0.7	09 March 2017	First Draft – Initial Data Management Plan (DMP)
V0.8	16 March 2017	Comments – Initial DMP
V0.9	30 March 2017	Draft – Initial DMP
V1.0	31 March 2017	Pre-final Version – Initial DMP
V1.1	19 April 2017	Review of the Steering Committee – Initial DMP
V1.2	20 April 2017	Final Version – Initial DMP
V2.0	14 February 2018	First update DMP
V2.1	17 October 2018	Second update DMP to comply with GDPR
V2.2	05 Nov 2018	Finalization of second update DMP to comply with GDPR
V2.3	11 Jan 2019	Revisions of DMP based on feedback from SC
V2.4	25 Jan 2019	Inclusion of information on handling of data through PREFER website interfaces
V2.5	01 Feb 2019	Revisions of DMP based on data management team meeting
V3.0	31 May 2022	Revision of DMP based on changed repository for long-term storage

² PU = Public, fully open

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1. Introduction and aim

The main objective of the Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER) project is to strengthen patient-centric decision making throughout the life cycle of medical products (a term which, in the context of this project, includes medicinal products (1) and medical devices (2)) by developing evidence-based recommendations to guide industry, regulatory authorities, health technology assessment (HTA) bodies and reimbursement agencies on how and when patient-preference studies could be performed, and how the results can be used to support and inform decision making.

The PREFER project structure includes four work packages (WPs) which jointly address the challenges for incorporating patient preferences in decision making. WP1 ensures the proper overall management of the project in order to strengthen and support the participants to achieve the objectives, complete the milestones in time, and provide the deliverables. WP2 seeks to understand stakeholder concerns, needs and insights around the use of patient preference studies, aiming to make recommendations towards WP3 about the methodologies that could be used in case studies. The general objective of WP 4 is to generate recommendations on patient-preference elicitation to inform benefit-risk decision making throughout the medicinal product life cycle, for industry, Regulatory Authorities, HTA bodies, and reimbursement agencies

The Description of Action (DoA) of PREFER (p.19-20) provides the general framework regarding data management, data protection, data sharing, ownership, accessibility, and sustainability requirements (4). In addition, the PREFER Consortium Agreement indicates that a specific DMP will be created in WP1. More specifically, the Consortium agreement indicated in section 7.5.4 the following:

'As an exception to Clause 29.3 of the Grant Agreement, as provided for in its last paragraph, certain Beneficiaries have indicated that their main objective in the Action would be jeopardized by making all or specific parts of the research data of the Action openly accessible. Beneficiaries have therefore agreed to a data management plan, which describes how data will be handled instead of open access, and which plan details the reasons for not giving open access. Such data management plan is a deliverable of Work Package 1 and shall be added as Appendix 7 to this Consortium Agreement' (3).

The DMP is an evolving document with the final DMP forming Appendix 7 of the Consortium Agreement, describing all aspects of how the data generated within PREFER were managed. Overall, the DMP provides a description of the data management that has been applied in the PREFER project including:

- a description of the data repositories, who is able to access the data, and who owns the data;
- the main DMP elements for each of the research projects (interviews, literature review, case study, etc.) contributing to PREFER, to be defined and provided to PREFER;
- the time period for which data must be stored;
- the standards for data collection and evaluation;
- the possibilities of and conditions for sharing data; and
- the implementation of data protection requirements.

In summary, the PREFER DMP gives guidance and provides an oversight of general data management, while each PREFER task/study needed to provide specific data management information including, but not limited to, data capture systems, data analysis systems, data protection and data privacy measures, including description of de-identification of data sets and access rules. In cases where the research results are not open access, a justification needs to be provided.

The final DMP (D1.9) reflects the data management procedures applied throughout the PREFER project. The main changes to the previous versions (1.3 and 1.6) are:

- ***Removal of the KU Leuven repository from DMP, as it was not used by research projects or case studies other than those where KU Leuven was study sponsor/data owner***
- ***Insertion of the Zenodo platform for open access, that is used for long-term storage of PREFER deliverables, thus replacing ALLVIS the Upsala University repository, which is removed from the DMP***

2. General principles

The DMP is a working document, that evolved during the PREFER project, and is updated to reflect project progress. Table 1 lists the deliverable version updates of the DMP for PREFER. Additional updates will be done whenever important changes occur e.g., due to the creation of new data sets.

Table 1 PREFER Data Management Plan (DMP) deliverables

Del. no.*	Deliverable name	WP no.	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery Date**
1.3	Initial DMP	1	Actelion	R	PU	6 (March 2017)
1.6	Update DMP	1	Actelion	R	CO	18 (March 2018)
1.9	Final DMP	1	Actelion	R	PU	plan: 60 (September 2020); actual: 31 May 2022

DMP= Data Management Plan; WP= Work packages; R = Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web; CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Grant Agreement

* According to the Table 3.1c (List of deliverables) of the PREFER Description of Action(4)

** Measured in months from the project start date (October 2016, Month 1)

The DMP follows the principles that research data are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) (5) as well as being attributable, legible, contemporaneous, original and accurate (ALCOA)(6). In 2018, this DMP was updated to comply with the new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (7). The terminology used in this DMP is explained in the glossary (Chapter 11 of this DMP). The general principles on access rules are defined in the Consortium Agreement (Section 8) (3).

For research data generated as part of an ongoing medicinal product development program within industry, there may be proprietary and privacy concerns that will be acknowledged, and agreements made with the respective partners on data accessibility and data storage. To acknowledge potential differences for industry or academic case studies the DMP will refer to “data generated in industry-led studies” and “data generated in academic-led studies”.

Responsibilities in ensuring compliance with regulations

PREFER funded some of the studies conducted in PREFER, but never is considered as the study sponsor. Study sponsors are either academic institutions in case of academic-led studies or companies in case of industry-led studies and are further listed in Chapter 6. Therefore, the study sponsors, and not PREFER, are responsible for ensuring compliance with regulations. Nevertheless, this DMP is provided by PREFER to inform its partners on best practices in data management.

3. Glossary

Term	Explanation
Access	The general principles on access rules are defined in the Consortium Agreement (Section 8) (3). These rules are different for research results to exploit and research results to disseminate and are further explained in chapter 2 of this DMP.
Born digital (data type)	The term born-digital refers to materials that originate in a digital form. This is in contrast to digital reformatting, through which analog materials become digital.
CentOS	CentOS (from Community Enterprise Operating System) is a Linux distribution that attempts to provide a free, enterprise-class, community-supported computing platform functionally compatible with its upstream source, Red Hat Enterprise Linux (RHEL).
Controller	'Controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by European Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by the European Union or Member State law (7).
Data owner	The Consortium Agreement regulates the ownership and access to key knowledge generated in the project (3). Each dataset that is or will be generated will have an owner responsible for its creation and/or management (registered as creator in the metadata). The responsibilities of the data owner are explained in Chapter 6.2.
Domain Name System (DNS)	DNS stands for Domain Name System, which is the largest digital database in the world, containing information about every web site on the internet. Every web site online has an IP address that is its actual internet location, and this number is used to locate the web site within the database. The data that tells the web server how to respond to your input is known as the DNS records, or zone files. These records play a vital role in the functionality of the internet, and any aspiring internet technology expert should learn the following facts about DNS records and how they are used.
Funding source	The funding source is defined as the source providing the financial support to conduct the study, e.g., for the PREFER case studies (RA, NMD, Lung Cancer) the funding source is PREFER.
IP address	An IP (Internet Protocol) address is an identifier assigned to each computer and other device (e.g., printer, router, mobile device, etc.) connected to a TCP/IP network that is used to locate and identify the node in communications with other nodes on the network.
Long-term data storage	Storage of PREFER data after the end of the PREFER project.
Model (data format)	Data generated in modelling studies.
Multimedia (data format)	The multimedia data include one or more primary media data types such as text, images, graphic objects (including drawings, sketches and illustrations) animation sequences, audio and video. Multimedia data consists of a variety of media formats or file representations including TIFF, BMP, PPT, IVUE, FPX, JPEG, MPEG, AVI, MID, WAV, DOC, GIF, EPS, PNG, etc. Because of restrictions on the conversion from one format to the other, the use of the data in a specific format has been limited as well. Usually, the data size of multimedia is large such as video; therefore, multimedia data often require a large storage.
Numerical (data format)	Files that contain decimal numbers and integer numbers (including negative values).
Observational (data type)	Data generated in observational research.
Personal data	'Personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (7).

Processing	'Processing' means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction (7).
Processor	'Processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller (7).
Pseudonymization	'Pseudonymisation' means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (7).
Random-access memory (RAM)	Random-access memory is a form of computer data storage which stores frequently used program instructions to increase the general speed of a system.
Recipient	'Recipient' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or another body, to which the personal data are disclosed, whether a third party or not. However, public authorities which may receive personal data in the framework of a particular inquiry in accordance with Union or Member State law shall not be regarded as recipients; the processing of those data by those public authorities shall be in compliance with the applicable data protection rules according to the purposes of the processing (7).
Reference (data type)	In programming language theory, a reference type is a data type that refers to an object in memory. In Java a reference data type is a variable that can contain the reference or an address of dynamically created object. In PREFER the data that classify as reference data are the references of the articles used for literature reviews.
Remote desktop protocol (RDP)	Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) is a proprietary protocol developed by Microsoft, which provides a user with a graphical interface to connect to another computer over a network connection. The user employs RDP client software for this purpose, while the other computer must run RDP server software.
Secure Shell (SSH)	Secure Shell (SSH) is a cryptographic network protocol for operating network services securely over an unsecured network. The best-known example application is for remote login to computer systems by users.
Sensitive personal data	Personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation (7).
Server Message Block (SMB) Protocol	A network file sharing protocol, and as implemented in Microsoft Windows is known as Microsoft SMB Protocol. The set of message packets that defines a particular version of the protocol is called a dialect. The Common Internet File System (CIFS) Protocol is a dialect of SMB.
Short-term storage	Storage of PREFER data during the PREFER project.
Simulation (data type)	Data generated in simulation studies.
Sponsor	Sponsor means the entity that takes responsibility for and initiates a clinical investigation. The sponsor may be an individual or company (e.g., pharmaceutical, medical device) any, governmental agency, academic institution, private organization, or other organization. The sponsor does not actually conduct the investigation unless the sponsor is a sponsor-investigator. A person other than an individual that uses one or more of its own employees to conduct an investigation that it has initiated is a sponsor, not a sponsor-investigator, and the employees are investigators
Textual (data format)	A text file (sometimes spelled "textfile": an old alternative name is "flatfile") is a kind of computer file that is structured as a sequence of lines of electronic text.
Virtual private network (VPN)	A virtual private network (VPN) extends a private network across a public network, such as the Internet. It enables users to send and receive data across shared or public networks as if their computing devices were directly connected to the private network. Applications running across the VPN may therefore benefit from the functionality, security, and management of the private network.

4. Overview of data managers, data repositories and access rules

Repositories / platforms used in the PREFER project. The responsible contacts are listed in table 2.

The platform “Projectplace” was the interaction platform for PREFER members to store and exchange reports and project documentation; will still be available after the end of the PREFER project for another 3 years until 31 May 2025 and can be used by the PREFER Expert Network. Project Place will continuously be hosted by Uppsala University.

In the DMP 1.3 and 1.6 the data repository at KU Leuven was proposed as data storage repository for PREFER studies such as interviews and focus groups with stakeholders and academic patient preference studies.

Finally, the data repository at KU Leuven (PREFER SharePoint) was only used to store and exchange sensitive personal and other study data where KU Leuven was the study sponsor.

Other study sponsors' data sets, containing personal data, were stored by the data owners in their own secure repository for a fixed period of time, as defined in the applicable laws or regulations. Details regarding data storage are described in the study specific data management plan (Chapter 6).

The main platform for open access of the PREFER deliverables is Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/>). This is a change from the original plan to use the Uppsala University repository (ALLVIS) for long term storage, therefore all sections describing ALLVIS in the previous versions (D1.3 and D1.6) of the DMP are removed from this final DMP (D1.9)

Access rules for future research is described in section 7: Sharing and secondary use of PREFER generated or collected data.

Table 2 Main contacts for data management aspects

Responsibilities	Name	E-mail address
Data Management compliance contact	Monika Brand	mbrand6@its.jnj.com
Deputy Data Management compliance contact (until Jun 2020)	Eline van Overbeeke	eline.vanoverbeeke@kuleuven.be
Projectplace contact	Carl Steinbeisser	carl@collaborate.eu
Deputy Projectplace contact	Josepine Fernow	josepine.fernow@crb.uu.se
Zenodo https://zenodo.org/communities/prefer/	Carl Steinbeisser	carl@collaborate.eu
PREFER website contact	Josepine Fernow	josepine.fernow@crb.uu.se
PREFER website deputy contact	Anna Holm	anna.holm@crb.uu.se
Data controllers for information submitted through website interfaces	Carl Steinbeisser	carl@collaborate.eu
	Josepine Fernow	Josepine.fernow@crb.uu.se

The WP1 data management team (see contributors on page 1 of this document) had the responsibility to update the names related to the responsibilities, as people might change position.

Study sponsors and WP leads were responsible for creation of study specific DMPs.

4.1 Projectplace

Projectplace is the platform used by PREFER to facilitate collaboration between PREFER members, to plan deliverables, to track progress of all tasks, and to store meeting minutes and task reports. All PREFER members have an account so they can access Projectplace. This platform is still available after the end of the PREFER project for another 3 years until 31 May 2025 and can be used by the PREFER Expert Network. Project Place will continuously be hosted by Uppsala University.

4.3 Zenodo the platform for open access

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. For each submission, a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable. (Reference: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zenodo> on January 16, 2022). The use of Zenodo for IMI project deliverables is supported by IMI. Link to the PREFER community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/prefer/>

4.4 Data collected through PREFER website interfaces

PREFER collected personal data through website interfaces for several administrative purposes, for example collecting e-mail addresses of people who want to subscribe to the project's newsletters, and registration handling for meetings and events. To ensure people who voluntarily submit personal data through different website/online interfaces (by filling out forms posted on the PREFER website, which could potentially be reached through links in on different websites, electronic communications or social media), we have posted a Data protection notice on the PREFER website: <http://imi-prefer.eu/contact/data-protection-notice> (Appendix I), which we link to from all the forms used to collect this data. All such forms also include a checkbox to allow us to handle the personal data submitted through the form.

For newsletters, personal data is typically handled through MailChimp (<https://mailchimp.com/>) and the form to collect contact information for this purpose also includes a link to information about MailChimp privacy practices (<https://mailchimp.com/legal/>). Newsletters include links to allow recipients to manage their subscriptions, and clearly communicate that they are sent and distributed through the MailChimp platform.

Registrations to different kinds of PREFER meetings are normally handled using either google forms, with the resulting participant lists stored on Projectplace, or collected in an InfoGlue website repository database managed by Uppsala University. All such InfoGlue databases generated through online forms need to be reported to the Uppsala University Data Protection Officer, with the purpose and type of data clearly described, and clearly stating the period for which the data should be stored.

5. Overview of data types generated and collected in PREFER

The data generated and collected during the PREFER project can be divided into two categories of decreasing confidentiality:

1. datasets containing personal data
2. datasets containing non-personal data

The data generated within the PREFER project are (a) primary data (original research data) produced by different stakeholder e.g., interviews and case studies, and (b) secondary data (reuse of existing data) such as database studies and literature reviews. Primary data are data sets more likely to contain personal data, while secondary data sets are more likely to containing non-personal data.

Patient data was generated and processed during the activities planned in WP 2, WP 3 and WP 4 (Table 3).

- **WP 2** generated datasets containing literature reviews, recorded interviews, transcriptions of interviews, and review of reports in preference research
- **WP 3** created datasets containing both aggregated and patient-level identified or de-identified data. These data could be created from historical case studies, prospective industry-led and academic-led case studies, surveys, as well as from simulation studies
- **WP 4** generated datasets containing literature reviews and data resulting from expert panel discussions and consultation rounds.

Appropriate strategies must put in place by the individual research project owners, to ensure (personal) data protection/privacy, and individual studies are asked to provide a small DMP as described in this general DMP of PREFER (Chapter 6). The processes were worked out and implemented between M6 and M18, in collaboration with task WP 3 task 3.1 to align the templates and to use synergies for research project descriptions.

The WP1 Data Management Team provided tools to generate a meta-data repository of all research projects in a format as outlined in Table 3 and with the support from the WP leads, or research project owners, respectively. This meta-data repository will be updated regularly (at least on a quarterly basis) and is the master file for more detailed information of each research project as described in Table 3.

The WP1 Data Management Compliance Contacts (Table 2) together with the WP leads ensured that all generated data sets, or research projects, respectively, will be gathered as described in this DMP.

Table 3 was updated as described in Chapter 6.

Table 3 Summary of the PREFER-generated data

Task*	Objective	Design	Type	Format	Re-use**	Origin	Ca***
2.1	Identifying desires, expectations, concerns and requirements of stakeholders about methodologies for PP elicitation and their use in decision making	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	2.3	Secondary	2
		Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	2.3	Primary	1
2.2	Determine processes, conditions, contextual factors that influence the utility and role of PP studies	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	2.3	Secondary	2
		Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	2.3	Primary	1
2.3	Identification of assessment criteria used at decision points throughout the DLC	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Secondary	2
		Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	/	Primary	1
2.4	Identification of preference elicitation methods	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	2.6	Secondary	2
		Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	2.6	Primary	1
2.5	1. Identification of educational/gamified tools	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Secondary	2
	2. Identification of psychological tools	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Secondary	2
	3. Presentation of risks	Literature review	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Secondary	2
2.7	Identification of candidate methodologies and criteria to assess empirical case and simulation studies	Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	/	Primary	1
3.3	Identifying and assessing historical case studies from industry partners	Review of historical case studies	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Secondary	2
3.3	Lessons learned survey of PREFER members with preference research experience.	Survey	Born digital, reference	Textual	/	Primary	1
3.4	Identifying and supporting prospective case studies from industry partners	PP case study	Origin see study specific DMP, observational	Qualitative, numerical, multimedia	/	Primary	1
3.5-3.7	Empirical case studies and simulation studies	PP case study	Origin see study specific DMP, observational + simulation	Qualitative, numerical, multimedia, models	/	Primary	1
3.8	Additional case studies	PP case study	Origin see study specific DMP, observational	Qualitative, numerical, multimedia	/	Primary	1
4.3	Expert panels on recommendations	Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	/	Primary	1
4.4	Consultation rounds on recommendations	Interviews	Born digital, observational	Multimedia + textual	/	Primary	1

PP= Patient preferences; DLC=Drug Life Cycle; Ca= Category;

* According to the description of the tasks and different work packages in the PREFER DoA document of 16/07/17.

** Displays in which other tasks of WP2 and WP3 the data are used.

*** The data produced and used during the PREFER project can be divided into two categories (Ca):

1. datasets containing (sensitive) personal data
2. datasets containing non-personal data

6. Operational data management requirements for PREFER research studies

Each sponsor of an academic-led PREFER study or PREFER funded study (interviews, literature review, surveys, case studies, etc.) needed to set-up a study specific DMP, including but not limited to data capture systems, data analysis systems, data protection and data privacy measures, including description of de-identification of data sets and access rules. If the research results could not be made open access a justification needed to be provided. Sponsors of industry-led studies were not required to use the study specific data management plan template as provided by PREFER, as they had their institutional templates to adhere to. Study teams (of academic-led and industry-led) case studies do not have to submit their data management plan to PREFER.

6.1 Requirements for the study specific DMP

All sponsors academic-led PREFER studies or PREFER funded studies needed to fill in the study specific DMP template (Appendix IV – Study Specific Data Management Plan template), containing the meta data and describing the data management of data sets. Metadata are specifications for data that provide the contextual information required to understand those data. Such specifications describe the structure, data elements, interrelationships and other characteristics of data, the data repository used, and need to be securely stored with the database.

6.2 Responsibilities of the sponsor

The preference study sponsor defined data ownership for "participant level data" and the "analysis data set":

- Data ownership of participant level data: solely owned by the institution, who generates these participant level data.
- Data ownership of the analysis dataset (coded data): needed to be defined in particular if the analysis dataset is jointly owned by a study team that is constituted by different institutions. The analysis dataset should be shared with the PREFER consortium if it is the funding source of the study and in agreement with the consortium agreement

Furthermore, the preference study sponsor nominated one or more data controllers to ensure alignment with GDPR.

The data owner per task is described in the study specific DMP. The controller of the respective research projects must ensure and is responsible to comply with all legal and ethical requirements for data collection, handling, protection and storage. This includes adherence to regulations, guidelines such as (but not limited to) GDPR, the EU clinical trial directive 2001/20/EC, Good Clinical Practice (GCP), Good Pharmacoepidemiology Practice (GPP), as applicable. Only the research controller will be granted access to the secure data repository of KU Leuven.

All data protection rules described in Chapter 8 of the DMP apply to the archiving of the results underlying PREFER publications and recommendation documents.

Table 4 Overview of sponsors, data owners, controllers and data repository used per task

Note: the PhD students (marked PhD in the table below) may have left the organizations, the controller responsibility is now with the respective mentor of the PhD student: Ardine de Wit g.a.dewit@umcutrecht.nl (UMC Utrecht), Esther de Bekker-Grob debekker-grob@bmg.eur.nl (Erasmus University Rotterdam), Isabelle Huys Isabelle.huys@kuleuven.be (KU Leuven), Jorien Veldwijk veldwijk@eshpm.eur.nl (Erasmus University Rotterdam)

Task Design	Sponsor and data owner	Controller	E-mail address
2.1 Literature review	KU Leuven	(PhD) Rosanne Janssens	Rosanne.janssens@kuleuven.be
Interviews	KU Leuven & EUR	(PhD) Rosanne Janssens	Rosanne.janssens@kuleuven.be
2.2 Literature review	KU Leuven	(PhD) Eline van Overbeeke	Eline.vanoverbeeke@kuleuven.be
Interviews	KU Leuven & EUR	(PhD) Eline van Overbeeke	Eline.vanoverbeeke@kuleuven.be
2.3 Literature review	EUR	(PhD) Chiara Whichello	whichello@bmg.eur.nl
Interviews	KU Leuven & EUR	(PhD) Chiara Whichello	whichello@bmg.eur.nl
2.4 Literature review	EUR	(PhD) Vikas Soekhai	v.soekhai@erasmusmc.nl
Interviews	EUR	(PhD) Vikas Soekhai	v.soekhai@erasmusmc.nl
2.5 Literature review	European Institute of Oncology	Selena Russo	Selena.Russo@ieo.it
3.3 Historical case studies	NA	Leo Russo	leo.russo@pfizer.com
3.4-3.8 RA case study	University of Birmingham & University of Erlangen	Birmingham: Research Governance, University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT Erlangen Dean of Medical Faculty: Markus F. Neurath	Birmingham: researchgovernance@contacts.bham.ac.uk Erlangen: m3direktion@uk-erlangen.de
3.4-3.8 NMD case study	Newcastle University; Gorman, Grainne	Gorman, Grainne	prefer.project@ncl.ac.uk
3.4-3.8 Lung cancer study	European Institute of Oncology	Serena Oliveri	Serena.oliveri@ieo.it
3.4-3.8 PAVING additional case study	KU Leuven	(PhD) Eline van Overbeeke	Eline.vanoverbeeke@kuleuven.be
3.4-3.8 Multiple Myeloma additional case study	KU Leuven	(PhD) Rosanne Janssens	rosanne.janssens@kuleuven.be
3.4-3.8 Additional case studies	Registered on HPSTR	NA	hpstr.org/landing?searchQuery=PREFER

TBD= To be discussed; NA= not applicable; EUR= Erasmus University Rotterdam; HPSTR= Health Preference Study and Technology Registry

* The datasets containing survey data and/or recorded and transcribed interviews generated by the industry-led case studies are by definition to be regarded as personal data and require safe storage and handling in accordance with national and European regulatory frameworks. The industry partner responsible for conducting the case study will be responsible for the secure storage of the personal data.

7. Sharing and secondary use of PREFER generated or collected data

7.1 General Access rules

PREFER is promoting the principle of open science and research sharing through peer reviewed publications, which are a valuable source for further research. If researchers wish to use PREFER generated data and results for future research, the following process should be followed:

- Researchers contact the corresponding author of the respective PREFER case study publication
- Alternatively, the main contact person (controller) of the respective PREFER case study can be found in Table 4
- The PREFER case study contact person will bring a reasonable request forward to the study sponsor or case study steering committee, as applicable, for review and decision of the data sharing request.

The data and result sharing requests will be reviewed and decided upon on a case-by-case basis, applying all respective data protection rules and regulations, and respecting potential intellectual property rights.

7.2 Re-use of PREFER data within the PREFER consortium

To achieve the objectives of PREFER, it is imperative to follow the collaborative approach the partners agreed on when signing the consortium agreement. This includes the necessity to share data from the individual research projects while respecting data protection and intellectual property of the partners' work.

For those individual research projects within PREFER that need to use data generated in another PREFER task, Table 4 contains the controller contact details to whom a requester can reach out if they need to access the results. Only when participants of e.g., patient preference studies or PREFER surveys agreed via informed consent that their study results may be used for secondary research and the data is pseudonymized/coded, the results can be shared. To obtain the agreement of participants to use their pseudonymized data for secondary research specific conditions are added to the information sheet and informed consent form template of PREFER (APPENDIX II & III).

7.3 Use of PREFER results or patient level data by third parties

Scientific organizations all over the world are promoting a principle of open science and sharing of research data. By making results public, duplicate research can be prevented and there is a possibility to combine data. Also, money and time can be saved. The PREFER-generated results will be a basis for further research.

For those external individual research projects wanting to use PREFER generated or collected results during the course of PREFER, the general access rules described under 7.1 should be followed.

8. Protection of personal data

The collection of personal data will be conducted under the applicable international, Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI), and national laws and regulations and requires previous written informed consent by the individual, i.e., with public and commercial entities and if applicable outside the EU in countries with lower data protection standards. To obtain the agreement of participants of e.g. patient preference studies or PREFER surveys to use their data for secondary use, specific conditions are added to the information sheet and informed consent form template of PREFER (APPENDIX II & III).

The information sheets and consent forms will inform participants on how their personal data will be managed (APPENDIX II & III). All studies funded by PREFER (core case studies and additional academic case studies) have to use the information sheet and consent form template. These templates need to be aligned with the local regulations. If the local regulations are stricter than the ones in the forms, the local regulations have to be applied. Industry-led case studies are not required to use the templates provided in this DMP, as they will have their institutional templates to adhere to.

PREFER researchers committed to the highest standards of data security and protection in order to preserve the personal rights and interests of study participants. They will adhere to the provisions set out in the:

- General data protection regulation (GDPR) entered into force on the 25th of May 2018 (7)
- Directive 2006/24/EC of 15 March 2006 on the retention of data generated or processed in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communication services or of public communications networks(9)
- Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications)(10)
- Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data(11)

To secure the confidentiality, accuracy, and security of data and data management, the following measures were taken:

- All personal data obtained within the academic-led case studies will be transmitted to partners within the consortium only after coding (pseudonymization). Keys to identification numbers will be held confidentially within the respective research units. In situations where re-identification of study participants becomes necessary, for example the collection of additional data, this will only be possible through the research unit and in cases where informed consent for such cases has been given.
- Personal data are entered to secure platforms at study sites. Data are processed only for the purposes outlined in the patient information and informed consent forms of the respective case studies. Use for other purposes will require explicit patient approval. Also, data are not transferred to any places outside the consortium without patient consent.
- Rules relating to sharing and secondary use of PREFER generated or collected data are defined (Chapter 7)
- None of the personal data will be used directly for commercial purposes, but the knowledge derived from the research using the personal data may be brought forward to such use as appropriate, and this process will be regulated by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, in accordance with any generally valid legislation and regulations.

The following points were considered to guide the protection of data within the PREFER project:

- (i) The sponsor providing personal data to the project shall verify that:
 - the initial collection of these data has been compliant with the requirements of the original purpose

- the collection and the provision of the data to the project meets all legal requirements to which the entity is subject
- further storage and processing of the data after completion of the research project is in compliance with applicable law

(ii) The sponsor which provides personal data to the project shall document any restriction of use or obligation applicable to these data (e.g., the limited scope of purpose imposed by the consent form) in the study/dataset specific DMP (Chapter 6).

(iii) The sponsor which uses personal data in the project shall be responsible to ensure that it has the right under the applicable data protection and other laws to perform the activities contemplated in the project.

(iv) Personal data shall always be collected, stored, and exchanged in a secure manner, through secure channels.

9. Ethical aspects

9.1 General ethical aspects

The participants of PREFER are requested to adhering to all relevant international, IMI, and national legislation and guidelines relating to the conduct of prospective case studies as detailed below.

All research activities within PREFER requiring approval on ethical and legal grounds through responsible local or national Ethics Committees and Regulatory Authorities will be conducted only after obtaining such approval. All ethics approvals will be submitted to IMI before commencement of any prospective case study. A report by the PREFER Ethics Advisory Board will be submitted to IMI within the periodic reports.

The proposed research will comply with the highest ethical standards, including those outlined in the Grant Agreement (Article 34 of the Model Grant Agreement) and the European Code of Conduct for Research integrity. The balance between the research objectives and the means used to achieve them will be given special attention. To ensure this, PREFER is supported by its Ethical Advisory Board. The Ethical Advisory Board will consist of four experts on ethics, law, and drug development representing the key areas of the project, including a patient representative. The Ethical Advisory Board will monitor the progress of the project and ensure a high standard of research by taking part in the annual General Assembly meetings. In addition, it will:

- provide expert support to the consortium in all relevant ethical questions
- ensure compliance with legislation and guidelines
- conduct regular project reviews
- issue recommendations to the consortium when appropriate

Researchers are requested to have appropriate training regarding Good Scientific, Good Clinical, Good Pharmacoepidemiology Practice Guidelines and the legal and regulatory framework described in the following sections.

9.2 Studies involving human participants

The methodologies for eliciting patient preferences were tested in prospective case studies. Each patient preference study required approval from the relevant ethical review boards with adherence to requirements related to informed consent and protection of privacy.

Our foremost principles for the conduct of any research involving human participants within PREFER were:

- respect for the rights, integrity, and privacy of patients
- protection of vulnerable patients
- continuous monitoring of patients' safety
- generation of meaningful, high-quality data
- timely publication of case study results

All research in PREFER involving human participants were conducted under the applicable international, IMI, and national laws and regulations and only after obtaining approval by the applicable local or national Ethics Committees and Regulatory Authorities. PREFER partners are committed to:

- the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR) (7)
- the Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects (Adopted by the 18th World Medical Association (WMA) General Assembly, Helsinki, Finland, June 1964, and last amended by the 64th WMA General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, October 2013)(12)
- the standards of the International Conference on Harmonisation on Good Clinical Practice(13)
- the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, ETS No. 164, Oviedo, 4 April 1997; and the Additional Protocol on Biomedical Research (CETS No. 195), 2005(14)

- the UNESCO: Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005)(15)
- Research with human participants was to be conducted in the applicable countries in accordance with national and international regulations. Preference studies regarding future risks or investigating how to balance benefits and risks may cause psychological distress e.g., for vulnerable patient groups. This implied that all studies conducted within the PREFER project had to take actions in order to be able to support/counsel patients appropriately. This was one of the requirements assigned to each leader of a clinical case study.
- As mentioned above PREFER sought to include a broad selection of patient populations, including vulnerable patients if necessary. For ethical reasons it is important that perspectives from these patient groups are also included, and that patients who may experience certain difficulties to get their voice heard and their preferences considered. Vulnerable patient populations may have been identified in the field of Neuromuscular disorders where many of the diagnosed diseases are rare, and the patients are not adults. This is also why the PREFER project had included a patient organization within this disease area, i.e., Muscular Dystrophy UK. They, as well as the other patient organisations, were asked to give extra attention to the situation of vulnerable patients and the how they are included in the case studies.

Patient information and informed consent procedures were to be approved by the relevant national or local ethics boards. Controllers collecting personal data for a prospective collaborative research project were responsible for informing the study participants about the project using the information sheet and informed consent form template of PREFER (APPENDIX II & III).

The research conducted in PREFER did not have the potential for malevolent/criminal/terrorist abuse. There were no other ethics issues identified beyond those discussed above. Any potential issues that may have arisen during the project duration was to be presented to the Ethics Advisory Board to ensure they are addressed by taking the appropriate organisational, legal, and regulatory steps.

10. References

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3. Consortium Agreement for [Patient Preferences In Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER)]. Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking; 2015.
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10. Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications); 2002 [cited 15 February 2017]. Available from: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0058&from=en>.
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14. Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine. Council of Europe; 1997 [cited 20 February 2017]. Available from: <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=090000168007cf98>.
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11. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full term
ALCOA	Attributable, legible, contemporaneous, original and accurate
Ca	Category
CentOS	Community Enterprise Operating System
CETS	Council of Europe Treaty Series
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
CPU	Central processing unit
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DLC	Drug Life Cycle
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNS	Domain Name System
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUR	Erasmus University Rotterdam
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GB	Gigabyte
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPP	Good Pharmacoepidemiology Practice
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HPSTR	Health Preference Study and Technology Registry
ICTS	Information and communications technology services
IP address	Internet Protocol address
KUL	University of Leuven (KU Leuven)
PI	Principal Investigator
PP	Patient preferences
PREFER	Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
RAM	Random-access memory
RDP	Remote desktop protocol
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SMB	Server Message Block
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Science
SSH	Secure Shell
TBA	To be announced
TBD	To be discussed
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UU	Uppsala University
VPN	Virtual private network
WMA	World Medical Association
WP	Work packages

APPENDICES

Appendix I – PREFER project data protection notice

The Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER) is a five year public-private research project under the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). This data protection notice informs you about how we process personal data you submit to the project via different www.imi-prefer.eu website interfaces such as contact- and registration forms.

The PREFER consortium is committed to user privacy and data protection. This means any personal data, that can directly or indirectly identify you as a person, will be processed in compliance with the European legislation - General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and national data protection laws. When you agree to submit your information to PREFER, we commit to processing your personal data in accordance with the purposes, requirements and restrictions we set out in this notice.

Data controllers

PREFER data controllers are the individuals or bodies that, either alone or together with others, determine the different purposes and means by which your personal data will be processed. PREFER data controllers for data submitted through web interfaces are:

- Carl Steinbeisser, PREFER project manager, Steinbeisser Project Management UG, carl@collaborate.eu
- Josepine Fernow, PREFER communications lead, Uppsala University, josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se

The purposes and legal basis for processing your personal data

The PREFER project will only process your personal data to

- engage you in consultations and events.
- share our results and other project outputs with you via e-mail, web, social media and newsletters.

We will only collect personal data that are necessary to achieve the processing purposes above. Your personal data will not be used for other purposes than those stated here. We will not share data with third parties, which in this case means people that are not in the PREFER project.

The primary legal basis for processing your personal data is your consent. It is important to know that you have the right to withdraw consent at any time. This will not have any negative consequences for you.

Who receives and processes your personal data

The personal information you enter here will be received and processed by Steinbeisser Project Management UG and Uppsala University. If it is required, this data may be processed by other members of the PREFER consortium. You will find a list of partners here: <http://imi-prefer.eu/partners/>. Access to information will be restricted to members of the consortium using access controls, which include secure logins to PREFER data repositories.

The period and nature of processing, and the rights of the individual:

The personal information you provide here will be used until the purpose for which it was collected ends, or the PREFER project ends. Your data may be archived for ten years after the project ends (31 September 2021), or until you withdraw your consent. After either of these points, your data will be deleted. In addition, you have the right to:

- request the controllers to give you access to the personal data pertaining to you that is in our possession.
- request the controllers to correct any errors in your personal data to ensure it is accurate.
- request that the controllers erase your personal data.
- request that the controllers restrict future processing of your personal data,
- object to processing of your personal data.
- data portability, which means that upon your request, the data controller should provide you with a copy of all the data that we have about you in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format.
- withdraw your consent at any time, as the processing of your personal data occurs based on your consent. At this point, we will cease further processing of your personal data. Please note that this does not affect the lawfulness of any processing that we have already performed (before you withdraw your consent).
- place a complaint with a supervisory authority, for example your national data protection authority.

By submitting my contact information to PREFER:

I acknowledge that I have been informed of my rights in relation to the processing of my personal data by the PREFER project and understand my rights:

I freely consent to the processing of my personal data by PREFER for the purposes listed above.

Appendix II – Information sheet template

Replace this textbox by the logotype of your own institution

prefer.
 PATIENT PREFERENCES

Information sheet

Instruction for completion (to be deleted in actual form): This is a template for the information sheet and contains boilerplate text to be used to comply with the GDPR regulations and needs to be aligned with your local regulations. If the local regulations are stricter than the ones in this form, the local regulations have to be applied. Please insert the respective information where the text is highlighted in yellow. Please ensure that you have a patient representative reviewed your final information sheet, to ensure well comprehended. If language has to be amended for better understanding ensure that the message remains the same.

PREFER project study: **Insert the study title here**

Head of research:

Insert main researcher's name
 Insert address
 Insert email address
 Insert phone number

Research co-ordinator:

Insert main researcher's name
 Insert address
 Insert email address
 Insert phone number

Contact person for your coded data (data controller) :

Insert contact person's name
 Insert address
 Insert email address
 Insert phone number

Dear Mr./Ms.,

You are being invited to voluntarily participate in a study on **XXX**. Your opinion on **XXX** will be asked. Before you confirm your participation in this study, we ask you to read this information sheet carefully. For any questions regarding this study, please contact one of the persons mentioned at the top of this form.

What is the purpose of the study?

Describe the aim and secondary objectives of the case study.

Who is conducting the study?

This study is conducted by researchers at the (**name of the institution of the head of research**) in collaboration with (**list partner institutions**). This study is part of the PREFER project. The Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER) project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 115966. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Is this study scientifically and ethically justified?

Provide information on the ethics committees that approved the study. Ethics committees verify if the rights of participants are respected by researchers during a study, if the balance between risks and benefits is beneficial for the participants and if the study is scientifically and ethically justified.

Do I have to participate?

Your participation is completely voluntary. You can refuse to participate. If you decide not to participate, this will not affect your current or future health care. Also participation in the study will not affect your current or future health care.

What is asked of me?

Describe:

- What participation in the study will look like (or will involve);
- How much time is asked of the participant;
- What sensitive information will be gathered (remove the types of sensitive data that will not be gathered): Information will be gathered on your personal treatment preferences, health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, your genetics, biometric data, sex life or sexual orientation;
- What other information will be collected (e.g. demographics such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, etc.);
- How data is gathered;
- And where the study will be conducted.

How will my personal data be kept confidential?

The data collected during the preference study XXX will be stored in a secured database at XXX. The study will adhere to the national and local data protection laws. Your identity and that of other participants will be kept strictly confidential. In the secured database where the information of all participants are kept and analyzed, information that could lead to your identification (e.g. list all personal identifiers that will be removed XXX) are removed and replaced by a number at time of the data entry/transcription XXX (Please describe the process and the time point for removal of the personal identifiers in your study. E.g. in the qualitative work it may be at time of transcription, and in the quantitative survey it will be done at time of data entry). This process is called coding and from the coded (pseudonymized) data you cannot be identified; thus, no reporting of your personal identifying information in reports or publications can happen.

How will my coded (pseudonymized) data be used?

Your coded data will be used to learn more about how patients perceive certain drugs and how they make choices between alternatives. In addition, your coded data may be used to answer future scientific research questions by PREFER partners, support submission dossiers to regulators, and in the design of future studies. The results will be analyzed by researchers and health care professionals. The researchers intend to publish the results in scientific journals and disseminate them via presentations at congresses or meetings.

How will my coded data be shared and transferred?

The researchers may share your coded data with PREFER partners, regulatory authorities as well as with partners with whom it is working to jointly conduct scientific research in other countries. The data protection laws in these countries may be less protective than data protection laws in the European Economic Area (EEA). With regards to transfers from the EEA to other countries, including the U.S, standards will be followed that have been established by the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), national and local laws.

How long will my personal data be stored?

Records containing your personal data and your coded data will be retained at the study site (XXX) for a period of maximum 15 years (this is the duration of storage of study data as mentioned in the PREFER Data Management Plan (DMP), but adapt if other local storage requirements apply) from the end of the study.

What rights do I have concerning my personal data?

If you would like to review, correct, update, restrict, object to the processing or delete personal data, or if you would like to receive an electronic copy of the personal data you have provided, you should contact one of the persons mentioned at the top of this form. Your request for data deletion will be addressed within 30 days after your request have been confirmed. Such request may not be fulfilled in case that deletion renders or seriously impairs the study objectives, or in the case that regulations and laws that apply to this research require this data to be retained. Please note that you may not be able to review some of the data until after the end of the study,

and a request to delete your personal data cannot be fulfilled in case regulations and laws require your personal data to be retained. You can request the contact persons mentioned at the top of this form to forward any questions, concerns or complaints you may have to the data protection officer of their institution. You also have the right to lodge a complaint to the data protection authority at [\[insert contact information to the local data protection authority\]](#).

Please contact the contact person mentioned at the top of this form for any questions regarding this study or to confirm your participation.

Thank you for your interest and participation!

Appendix III – Informed consent form template

Replace this textbox by
 the logotype of your
 own institution

prefer.
 PATIENT PREFERENCES

Informed consent form

Instruction for completion (to be deleted in actual form): This is a template for the informed consent and needs to be aligned with your local regulations. If the local regulations are stricter than the ones in this form, the local regulations have to be applied. Please insert the respective information where the text is highlighted in yellow

PREFER project: **Insert the study title here**

Head of research: **Insert main researcher's name**
Insert address
Insert email address
Insert phone number

Funding acknowledgement: This study is part of the PREFER project. The Patient Preferences in Benefit-Risk Assessments during the Drug Life Cycle (PREFER) project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 115966. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Please read the terms below. If you agree to the terms, please tick the box at the bottom of this stage to confirm your participation.

Terms:

- I have read the information sheet version **XX** regarding this study and I have had an opportunity to ask questions or discuss any concerns about it;
- I was given sufficient time to decide whether I am willing to participate in this study;
- I am aware that participating in this study is completely voluntary and deciding not taking part will not affect my current or future health care;
- I am aware that although I may be answering questions about medical products these responses will not lead to any change on my current health care nor to a drug prescription;
- I am aware that I can stop participating in this study at any time without affecting my current or future health care;
- I give permission for the researchers in the team to collect information about me as described in the information sheet version **XX**, **remove the types of sensitive data that will not be gathered:** including information on my personal treatment preferences, health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, your genetics, biometric data, sex

Appendix IV – Study Specific Data Management Plan template

Placeholder
for logo

Study Specific Data Management Plan

Study title: *Insert the study title here*

Possibly add Approver Name with Signature appended, similar to protocol, when 'signed-off' on by the approver

This Study Specific Data Management Plan (DMP) Template describes all information on data management that has to be documented for studies involving human subjects. Sponsors need to fill in this template to create a Study Specific DMP. The Study Specific DMP will contain information on the metadata and data management of data sets created in that study. Metadata are specifications for data that provide the contextual information required to understand those data. Such specifications describe the structure, data elements, interrelationships and other characteristics of data, the data repository used, and need to be securely stored in a database.

Instructions on how to create a Study Specific Data Management Plan

A Study Specific DMP needs to be created per study. The text in *blue and Italic* in the Study Specific DMP template gives guidance on what information should be provided and should be replaced. It is recommended to set-up a Study Specific DMP prior to study initiation to record all information available regarding data management. The Study Specific DMP can then be updated at major study milestones (start qualitative phase, start quantitative phase, prior to analysis, changes in sponsors/data owners/controllers) when changes occur.

Study Specific Data Management Plan for [INSERT STUDY TITLE]

General Overview	
Title	<i>Name of the study</i>
Research sponsor	<i>Names of the entity that takes responsibility for and initiates a clinical investigation. The sponsor may be an individual or pharmaceutical company, governmental agency, academic institution, private organization, or other organization.</i>
Name of data owner	<p><i>Name and affiliation of the data owner. Format: Organization; Surname, First name.</i></p> <p><i>Each dataset that is or will be generated will have an owner responsible for its creation and/or management (registered as creator in the metadata).</i></p> <p><i>Data ownership can be defined on different levels:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Data ownership of participant level data: solely owned by the institution, who generates these participant level data.</i> <i>Data ownership of the analysis dataset (coded data): needs to be defined, in particular, if the analysis dataset is jointly owned by a study team that is constituted by different institutions.</i>
Email address of data owner	<i>Please provide the email address of the data owner.</i>
Name of controller	<i>Name and affiliation of the controller. Format: Organization; Surname, First name. 'Controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.</i>
Email address of controller	<i>Please provide the email address of the controller.</i>
Funding source	<i>Provide information regarding financial support such as research grants, or indicate if the sponsor funds the study.</i>
Start and end date	<i>Start and end date of the study. Format: dd.mm.yyyy – dd.mm.yyyy.</i>
Method	<i>How the data are generated, listing equipment and software used (including model and version numbers), formulae, algorithms, experimental protocols, and other things one might include in a lab notebook. Examples: interviews, transcribed verbatim, analysed in Nvivo (version); or online survey, analysed in Excel.</i>
Standards	<p><i>Reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline can be made. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created. Depending on type of data, different standards for collection exist, including but not limited to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Systematic literature review: Cochrane and Joana Bridge institute standards</i> <i>Interviews: QUAGOL</i> <i>Focus group discussion: AMEE 91 guide</i> <i>Patient preference studies: depending on the type of method, e.g. ISPOR guide for DCE.</i>
Type of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Datasets containing personal data</i> <i>Datasets containing non-personal data</i>

Processing	<i>How the data will be altered or processed, including processes of pseudonymization.</i>
Data source (if applicable)	<i>Citations to data derived from other sources, including details of where the source data is held and how it was accessed.</i>
Content Description	
Data description	<i>Keywords or phrases describing the dataset or content of the data. Indicate version number if applicable. Describe the nature and origin of the data.</i>
Language	<i>All languages used in the dataset.</i>
Variable list (if applicable)	<i>Description with variable name, length, type, etc. and code lists. Example: SEX, length of field (1 or more characters), values: F for female; M for male. AGE, length of field (1 or more characters), values: yy. A reference to a document in which these variables are described can be included as an alternative to listing the variables here (for example the survey/questionnaire).</i>
Data quality	<i>This section should include a description of data quality standards and procedures to assure data quality (example: references to guidelines followed to design interview guides/Discreet Choice Experiments/etc.).</i>
Code list	<i>Explanation of codes or abbreviations used in either the file names or the variables in the data files (e.g. '999 indicates a missing value in the data').</i>
Technical Description	
Repository	<i>Mention where the data is stored.</i>
File Formats	<i>Formats of the data, e.g. FITS, SPSS, HTML, JPEG.</i>
File structure	<i>Organization of the data file(s) and layout of the variables, where applicable.</i>
Checksum/audit trial	<i>A digest value computed for each file that can be used to detect changes; if a recomputed digest differs from the stored digest, the file must have changed. This section should describe how it is ensured that if data are changed, that this change is then documented.</i>
Necessary software	<i>Names of any special-purpose software packages required to create, view, analyse, or otherwise use the data.</i>
Access	
Rights	<i>The sponsor should indicate which access rights are applicable. Any known intellectual property rights, statutory rights, licences, or restrictions on use of the data.</i>
Access information	<i>Where and how your data can be accessed by other researchers.</i>
Sharing	<i>Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating, in particular, the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). If the dataset cannot be shared or made open access, the reasons</i>

	<i>for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).</i>
Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup)	<i>Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.</i>

Version and Revisions

Version	Date	Description
<i>V1 [add .# for minor version changes and V# for major version changes]</i>	<i>XX Month YYYY</i>	